

EFFECT OF PHASE SHIFT ON THE RESPONSE OF LAMINATED WOVEN COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This research focuses on responses of 64 woven laminated composites whose phase shift in microstructure is different under uniaxial compression and biaxial compression. The motivation of this paper is to understand how the microstructure arrangement affects laminate responses, particularly on the maximum strength and the tangential stiffness. Each laminated composite consists of four layers of laminae. Each layer of lamina has the same constituent microstructures. The laminae in different layers are shifted in the x and y direction to create phase shift. The first (bottom) layer of lamina in laminates remains stationary while the second layer of lamina, third layer of lamina, and fourth (top) layer of lamina are shifted in the x direction by 0mm, 2mm, 4mm, and 5mm, respectively. The results show that, under uniaxial compression, phase shift has significant influence on the homogenized tangential stiffness and has significant influence on the maximum failure strength. Under biaxial compression, phase shift also affects maximum strength. No significant difference on the tangential modulus of different laminates is observed under biaxial compression. By optimally arranging phase shift, the maximum strength of laminates under uniaxial compression or biaxial compression can be reached. For laminates consisting of the same microstructures in each layer of lamina, merely using homogenized modulus obtained from one layer of lamina cannot predict the responses of multi-layer-laminae composites due to phase shift.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymer matrix based textile fiber composites (TFC), compared to conventional continuous fiber composites, are getting more attention due to tunable microstructures to achieve the desired material properties. Detailed introduction to TFC can be seen in [1] and [2]. Obtaining the mechanical properties of textile composites from inhomogeneous microstructures is important to engineers. To analyze textile composites, the first step is to identify the microstructures so that the corresponding material properties such as, Young's modulus can be obtained. Different methods have been used to get information of initial stiffness (Young's modulus) from microstructures. An approximation method, mosaic method [3], is used in different piecewise rectangular blocks to describe complex microstructures and the authors point out that the modified mosaic parallel model fails to describe composites with large interlaced regions. Fiber undulation and continuity are used along both the warp and weft directions and 2D woven fiber properties are predicted well [4]. An analytical model is used for the calculation of effective linear elastic stiffness of a 2D triaxial flat braided composite (2DTBC) and imperfection in the fiber tow is also included in the analytical model [5].

The influence of various parameters such as braid angle, waviness ratio, material properties, and cross-sectional shape on the effective engineering properties of the braided composites is reported [6]. The internal geometry of 2D woven fabrics is used as a unit-cell geometry preprocessor for meso-mechanical models of composite materials [7]. It is to be noted that majority of literature on the homogenized modulus, including the paper just mentioned [3], [4], [5], and [6], focuses on initial homogenized modulus. In fact, once accurate volume fraction of each constituents is available, initial homogenized stiffness can be calculated either by analytical methods or numerical methods. The responses and homogenized modulus of composites under finite strain have been studied in [8], [9],

and [10]. In [9], a novel analysis of microscopic instability and bifurcation phenomena is developed in the context of homogenization theory of finitely deformed periodic elastic composites containing micro-cracks in unilateral self-contact. In [10], the strong role of crack self-contact nonlinearities and the influence of microscopic defects on the homogenized composite properties is investigated.

Besides stiffness, failure strength of composites is also of interest to engineers. Because various microstructures can be designed and manufactured in textile composites, the influence of the microstructure arrangement on the failure strength has caught attention from researchers. It is reported that weave architectures have significant influence on the progressive failure behaviors even if the composites have the same overall fiber volume fraction, tow waviness and tow cross-section [11]. Weave architecture and internal geometry affect location and morphology of the damage initiation [12]. Different sizes of representative unit cells are used to study progressive failure on textile composites [13]. The influence of parameters such as yarn size, yarn spacing, yarn crimp, braid angle, and overall fiber volume fraction on the strength properties of textile composites is studied [14]. These papers mentioned above, [11], [12],[13], and [14], indicate the importance of including the microstructure details for accurately predicting the responses of composites.

Although it is desirable to include detailed microstructures as many as possible in simulations, in the progressive failure analysis at the structural level, it is computationally expensive to include all microstructure details. Therefore, it is computationally less expensive to use homogenized material properties of a representative unit cell if such periodicity of a unit cell can be found. For example, one layer of plane weave lamina in Figure 1 can be approximated as a homogenized orthotropic material. This is because the angle between fiber tows in the local principal direction and another local principal direction is 90 degree in a unit cell. If one had a laminated composite made from the several layers of laminae where each layer of lamina has the same constituent microstructures, one could treat the whole composite as homogeneous orthotropic materials. It suffices to use the homogenized modulus from one layer of lamina to represent the modulus for the whole laminate. This concept of homogenization is exactly what the class laminate theory is based on. However, using homogenized modulus from one layer of lamina may neglect the influence of phase shift among different layers of laminae. The influence of phase shift on the responses of laminated composites has rarely been studied in the literature. In terms of the definition of phase shift in this paper, phase shift is defined as two laminae having the same constituent microstructures stacked in the z direction but one lamina is shifted in the x-y plane relative to another lamina. In the literature, there is a terminology similar to phase shift called nesting. The definition of nesting refers to the change of microstructures within the representative unit cell. Nesting usually comes with the change of volume fraction of constituents in a unit cell. The influence of nesting, such as flatness of the yarns, tightness and balance of the fabric, fabric weaving, braiding, knitted pattern, number of layers and degree of shear has been studied by [15]. Particularly, the authors point out that nesting effect becomes more pronounced with the decrease of the fabric tightness and the decrease of the float length in the weave. When nesting is introduced, the stiffness for the in-phase and out-of-phase configuration of the layers differs by 10% to 20%. This change roughly corresponds to the change in fiber volume fraction caused by the nesting [16]. It is to be noted that the nesting discussed in in [15], [17], and [16] is due to the volume fraction change of fiber tows in a unit cell. The phase shift in this paper doesn't involve volume fraction change in constituent microstructures in each layer of lamina. The influence of phase shift on laminated woven composites using 2D models is studied in [18] and the authors conclude that woven laminates with phase shift have higher strength than those without phase shift.

On the one hand, using homogenized modulus for simulations is required to save computation cost. On the other hand, including microstructures is important and essential to accurately predict the progressive failure of composites. The motivation of this research is to study the role of phase shift among laminae on the responses of woven laminates under uniaxial compression and biaxial compression. This paper is organized as follow: How the four-layer-laminae woven composites with different phase shift are created is explained first. This is followed by how the finite elements analysis is being conducted in ABAQUS. Results of different laminated composites under uniaxial compression and biaxial compression will be discussed. Finally, conclusions will be made..

Figure 1: Single layer of woven lamina

Figure 2: Representative unit cell

2 REPRESENTATIVE UNIT CELL

The representative unit cell (RUC) of a laminate consists of four layers of laminae. Each layer of lamina has the dimension of 10 mm in the x and y (in plane) direction and 1.5 mm in the z (thickness) direction in Figure 2. Each lamina has four fiber tows, two are undulated along the x direction and two are undulated along the y direction. Each fiber tow is described by a sinusoidal function with an elliptical cross section whose a is 4mm for the major axis and b is 0.4 mm in the minor axis. The undulated sinusoidal curve and the elliptical cross section is based on the microstructures of a woven composites specimen in Figure 3.

In order to account for composites surrounding the representative unit cell in the x-y plane, periodic boundary conditions in the x direction and y direction are imposed in the finite element implementation. To study the influence of phase shift, the first (bottom) layer of the lamina remains fixed while the second layer, the third layer, and the fourth layer are shifted by 0 mm, 2 mm, 4 mm, and 5 mm, respectively. In Figure 4, the top meshes are the laminate whose phase shift is 0 mm in the 2nd layer, phase shift is 2 mm in the 3rd layer, and phase shift is 0 mm in the fourth layer. The bottom meshes are the laminate whose phase shift is 2 mm in the 2nd layer, phase shift is 2 mm in the 3rd layer, and phase shift is 0 mm in the fourth layer. In Figure 5, the top meshes are the laminate whose phase shift is 4 mm in the 2nd layer, phase shift is 2 mm in the 3rd layer, and phase shift is 0mm in the fourth layer. The bottom meshes are for the laminate whose phase shift is 5 mm in the 2nd layer, phase shift is 2 mm in the 3rd layer, and phase shift is 0 mm in the fourth layer. Because 4 phase shifts can be imposed in each layer of lamina, total of 64 laminates can be established with a combination of phase shift in 2nd layer, 3rd layer, and 4th layer.

Figure 3: Representative unit cell

Figure 4: The top meshes are the laminate whose phase shift in the 2nd layer is 0mm, phase shift in the 3rd layer is 3mm, phase shift in the 4th layer is 0mm. The bottom meshes are the laminate whose phase shift in the 2nd layer is 2mm, phase shift in the 3rd layer is 2mm, phase shift in the 4th layer is 0mm

Figure 5: The top meshes are the laminate whose phase shift in the 2nd layer is 4mm, phase shift in the 3rd layer is 2mm, phase shift in the 4th layer is 0mm. The bottom meshes are the laminate whose phase shift in the 2nd layer is 5mm, phase shift in the 3rd layer is 2mm, phase shift in the 4th layer is 0mm

3 FINITE ELEMENT IMPLEMENTATION

Finite element analyses are conducted by ABAQUS [19]. Each layer of lamina consists of 48000 C3D8 elements and total of 192000 C3D8 elements are in a laminate. Fiber tows locally are simulated as elastic, transversely isotropic materials with the following engineering constants $E_1=121\text{GPa}$, $E_2=36.1\text{GPa}$, $E_3=36.1\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{12}=0.2$, $\nu_{23}=0.1$, $\nu_{13}=0.2$, $G_{12}=39.5\text{GPa}$, $G_{23}=65.7\text{GPa}$, and $G_{13}=39.5\text{GPa}$. The matrix is assumed to be isotropic, elastic-perfectly plastic materials with $E=3\text{GPa}$ and plastic strain initiation is 0.02. Riks arc-length is used to track the post failure equilibrium path. Periodic boundary conditions in conjunction with macroscopic deformation gradient are imposed following the procedures in [20].

4 UNIAXIAL COMPRESSION

Four groups are defined and each group has 4 laminates whose corresponding phase shift (microstructure arrangement) is different. In group 1, the laminates whose phase shift in the 2nd layer is 0mm, 2mm, 4mm, and 5mm, respectively while phase shift in the 3rd layer is 0mm and phase shift in the 4th layer is 0mm. In group 2, the laminates whose phase shift in the 2nd layer is 0mm, 2mm, 4mm, and 5mm, respectively while phase shift in 3rd layer is 2mm and phase shift in the 4th layer is 0mm. In group 3, the laminates whose phase shift in the 2nd layer is 0mm, 2mm, 4mm, and 5mm, respectively while phase shift in 3rd layer is 4mm and phase shift in the 4th layer is 0mm. In group 4, the laminates whose phase shift in the 2nd layer is 0mm, 2mm, 4mm, and 5mm, respectively while phase shift in 3rd layer is 5mm and phase shift in the 4th layer is 0mm.

The 16 laminates in group 1, group 2, group 3, and group 4 have one common feature. That is, no phase shift is imposed in the 4th layer of lamina. Following the same procedures, 16 laminates are created when phase shift in the 4th lamina is 2mm, 16 laminates are created when phase shift in the fourth lamina is 4mm, 16 laminates are created when phase shift in the fourth lamina is 5mm. The maximum strength for each laminate among these 64 laminates is summarized in Table 1 and Table 2. The highest maximum strength is 8.7×10^8 Pa when phase shift is 5 mm in the 4th layer, phase shift is 0 mm in the 3rd layer, and phase shift is 5 mm in the 2th layer. The lowest maximum strength is 3.7×10^8 Pa when phase shift is 4 mm in the 4th layer, phase shift is 0 mm in the 3rd layer, and phase shift is 2 mm in the 2th layer. From the point of view of homogenization, these 64 laminates have the same volume fraction of constituent microstructures at the scale of lamina. It is expected to have close, if not the same, maximum strength and tangential stiffness. However, the results indicate that homogenized modulus obtained from one layer of lamina is not sufficient to represent the responses of 64 laminates.

Π_{11} vs F_{11} for 4 laminates in group 1 is in Figure 6. In Figure 6, the laminate whose phase shift is 0mm in the 2nd layer has the lowest maximum strength whereas the laminate whose phase shift is 5mm in the 2nd layer has the highest maximum strength. The difference between highest maximum strength and lowest maximum strength of laminates in group 1 is more than 70%. Initially, the homogenized tangential modulus are the same for laminates which have different phase shift. This is consistent with the conclusion in the literature for homogenized initial tangential stiffness as the initial stiffness is determined by the volume fraction of constituents. Because all of the laminates have the same volume fraction of fibers and matrix, there is no surprise that all laminates have the same initial tangential stiffness. However, as the deformation increases, the tangential stiffness of laminates with different phase shifts changes. It can be seen that the stiffness of composites without phase shift has the lowest tangential stiffness as compression increases. One can also conclude the change of tangential modulus is due to phase shift (microstructure arrangement) not due to volume fraction of constituents.

Figure 7, Figure 8, and Figure 9 show the responses for laminates in group 2, group 3, and group 4. In each group (from group 1 to group 4), one can see that the laminate whose phase shift is 5mm in the 2nd layer has the highest maximum strength. The laminate whose phase shift is 0mm has the lowest maximum strength in the group 1 and group 2 whereas the laminate whose phase shift is 2mm has the lowest maximum strength in the group 3 and group 4. The value of maximum strength and minimum strength in each group changes as the phase shift changes.

Figure 6: The comparison of First Piola Kirchoff stress $|\Pi_{11}|$ vs Deformation gradient $|F_{11} - 1|$ for laminates under uniaxial compression. Phase shift in 4th layer=0 mm, Phase shift in 3rd layer=0 mm, Phase shift in 2nd layer are 0 mm, 2mm, 4mm , and 5mm.

Figure 7: The comparison of First Piola Kirchoff stress $|\Pi_{11}|$ vs Deformation gradient $|F_{11} - 1|$ for laminates under uniaxial compression. Phase shift in 4th layer=0 mm, Phase shift in 3rd layer=2mm Phase shift in 2nd layer are 0 mm, 2mm, 4mm , and 5mm.

Figure 8: The comparison of First Piola Kirchoff stress $|\Pi_{11}|$ vs Deformation gradient $|F_{11} - 1|$ for laminates under uniaxial compression. Phase shift in 4th layer=0 mm, Phase shift in 3rd layer=4 mm, Phase shift in 2nd layer are 0 mm, 2mm, 4mm , and 5mm.

Figure 9: The comparison of First Piola Kirchoff stress $|\Pi_{11}|$ vs Deformation gradient $|F_{11} - 1|$ for laminates under uniaxial compression. Phase shift in 4th layer=0 mm, Phase shift in 3rd layer=5mm Phase shift in 2nd layer are 0 mm, 2mm, 4mm , and 5mm.

4 BIAXIAL COMPRESSION

Four groups are defined and each group has four laminates. In group 5, the laminates whose phase shift in the 2nd layer is 0mm, 2mm, 4mm, and 5mm, respectively while phase shift in 3rd layer is 0mm and phase shift in the 4th layer is 0mm. In group 6, the laminates whose phase shift in the 2nd layer is 0mm, 2mm, 4mm, and 5mm, respectively while phase shift in 3rd layer is 2mm and phase shift in the 4th layer is 0mm. In group 7, the laminates whose phase shift in the 2nd layer is 0mm, 2mm, 4mm, and 5mm, respectively while phase shift in 3rd layer is 4mm and phase shift in the 4th layer is 0mm. In group 8, the laminates whose phase shift in the 2nd layer is 0mm, 2mm, 4mm, and 5mm, respectively while phase shift in 3rd layer is 5mm and phase shift in the 4th layer is 0mm.

In Figure 10, the laminate whose phase shift is 2mm in the 2nd layer has the lowest maximum strength whereas the laminate whose phase shift is 5mm in the 2nd layer have the highest maximum strength. The difference between highest maximum strength and lowest maximum strength of laminates in group 5 is more than 15 %, which is not much compared to the laminates having the same microstructures in group 1 under uniaxial compression.

Under uniaxial compression, the difference between the highest maximum strength and the lowest maximum strength of laminates in group 1 is around 70 %. Comparing the tangential homogenized modulus for different laminates doesn't show much change under biaxial compression. This result is

different from the result under uniaxial compression. During uniaxial compression, tangential homogenized modulus changes in different laminates. Figure 11, Figure 12, and Figure 13 show the responses for laminates in group 6, group 7, and group 8. Among laminates in these four groups, the laminate whose phase shift is 5mm in the 2nd layer has the highest maximum strength in both group 5 and group 6. The laminate whose phase shift is 0mm in the 2nd layer has the highest maximum strength in both group 7 and group 8.

16 laminates in group 5, group 6, group 7, and group 8 are built while no phase shift is in the 4th layer. Following the same procedures, additional 16 laminates whose phase shift is 2mm in the 4th layer can be created. 16 laminates whose phase shift is 4mm in the 4th layer can be created. 16 laminates whose phase shift is 5mm in the 4th layer can be created. The maximum strength of all laminates under biaxial compression is summarized in Table 3 and Table 4. The highest maximum strength is 8.4×10^8 Pa when phase shift is 5 mm in the 4th layer, phase shift is 0 mm in the 3rd layer, and phase shift is 5 mm in the 2nd layer. The lowest maximum strength is 6.5×10^8 Pa when phase shift is 0 mm in the 4th layer, phase shift is 2 mm in the 3rd layer, and phase shift is 2 mm in the 2nd layer. The results echo the observation in uniaxial compression, which is "homogenized modulus obtained from one layer of lamina is not sufficient to represent the responses of 64 laminates".

Figure 10: The comparison of First Piola Kirchhoff stress $|\Pi_{11}|$ vs Deformation gradient $|F_{11}-1|$ for laminates under biaxial compression. Phase shift in 4th layer=0 mm, Phase shift in 3rd layer=0 mm, Phase shift in 2nd layer are 0 mm, 2mm, 4mm , and 5mm.

Figure 11: The comparison of First Piola Kirchhoff stress $|\Pi_{11}|$ vs Deformation gradient $|F_{11}|$ for laminates under biaxial compression. Phase shift in 4th layer=0 mm, Phase shift in 3rd layer=2mm Phase shift in 2nd layer are 0 mm, 2mm, 4mm , and 5mm.

Figure 12: The comparison of First Piola Kirchhoff stress $|\Pi_{11}|$ vs Deformation gradient $|F_{11}|$ for laminates under biaxial compression. Phase shift in 4th layer=0 mm, Phase shift in 3rd layer=4 mm, Phase shift in 2nd layer are 0 mm, 2mm, 4mm , and 5mm.

Figure 13: The comparison of First Piola Kirchhoff stress $|\Pi_{11}|$ vs Deformation gradient $|F_{11}|$ for laminates under biaxial compression. Phase shift in 4th layer=5 mm, Phase shift in 3rd layer=2mm Phase shift in 2nd layer are 0 mm, 2mm, 4mm , and 5mm.

Table 1: Maximum strength of laminates under uniaxial compression

Phase Shift 4th layer (mm)	Phase Shift 3th layer (mm)	Phase Shift 2th layer (mm)	Maximum strength (Pa)	Phase Shift 4th layer (mm)	Phase Shift 3th layer (mm)	Phase Shift 2th layer (mm)	Maximum strength (Pa)
0 mm	0mm	0mm	4.0×10^8	4 mm	0mm	0mm	5.0×10^8
0 mm	0mm	2mm	4.2×10^8	4 mm	0mm	2mm	3.7×10^8
0 mm	0mm	4mm	5.6×10^8	4 mm	0mm	4mm	5.8×10^8
0 mm	0mm	5mm	7.0×10^8	4 mm	0mm	5mm	7.5×10^8
0 mm	2mm	0mm	4.2×10^8	4 mm	2mm	0mm	4.8×10^8
0 mm	2mm	2mm	4.2×10^8	4 mm	2mm	2mm	4.5×10^8
0 mm	2mm	4mm	5.5×10^8	4 mm	2mm	4mm	5.0×10^8
0 mm	2mm	5mm	6.7×10^8	4 mm	2mm	5mm	5.9×10^8
0 mm	4mm	0mm	5.5×10^8	4 mm	4mm	0mm	5.1×10^8
0 mm	4mm	2mm	5.2×10^8	4 mm	4mm	2mm	4.7×10^8
0 mm	4mm	4mm	5.7×10^8	4 mm	4mm	4mm	5.0×10^8
0 mm	4mm	5mm	6.7×10^8	4 mm	4mm	5mm	4.7×10^8
0 mm	5mm	0mm	6.9×10^8	4 mm	5mm	0mm	6.0×10^8
0 mm	5mm	2mm	6.7×10^8	4 mm	5mm	2mm	5.2×10^8
0 mm	5mm	4mm	6.8×10^8	4 mm	5mm	4mm	5.3×10^8
0 mm	5mm	5mm	7.8×10^8	4 mm	5mm	5mm	5.9×10^8
2 mm	0mm	0mm	4.3×10^8	5 mm	0mm	0mm	5.8×10^8
2 mm	0mm	2mm	4.3×10^8	5 mm	0mm	2mm	5.8×10^8
2 mm	0mm	4mm	5.3×10^8	5 mm	0mm	4mm	6.8×10^8
2 mm	0mm	5mm	7.1×10^8	5 mm	0mm	5mm	8.7×10^8
2 mm	2mm	0mm	4.2×10^8	5 mm	2mm	0mm	5.1×10^8
2 mm	2mm	2mm	4.2×10^8	5 mm	2mm	2mm	4.9×10^8
2 mm	2mm	4mm	3.8×10^8	5 mm	2mm	4mm	5.2×10^8
2 mm	2mm	5mm	6.0×10^8	5 mm	2mm	5mm	6.1×10^8
2 mm	4mm	0mm	5.0×10^8	5 mm	4mm	0mm	5.7×10^8
2 mm	4mm	2mm	4.7×10^8	5 mm	4mm	2mm	5.0×10^8
2 mm	4mm	4mm	5.0×10^8	5 mm	4mm	4mm	3.7×10^8
2 mm	4mm	5mm	5.8×10^8	5 mm	4mm	5mm	6.2×10^8
2 mm	5mm	0mm	4.8×10^8	5 mm	5mm	0mm	6.0×10^8
2 mm	5mm	2mm	4.0×10^8	5 mm	5mm	2mm	5.2×10^8
2 mm	5mm	4mm	5.5×10^8	5 mm	5mm	4mm	5.3×10^8
2 mm	5mm	5mm	6.2×10^8	5 mm	5mm	5mm	5.8×10^8

Table 2: Maximum strength of laminates under biaxial compression

Phase Shift 4th layer (mm)	Phase Shift 3th layer (mm)	Phase Shift 2th layer (mm)	Maximum strength (Pa)	Phase Shift 4th layer (mm)	Phase Shift 3th layer (mm)	Phase Shift 2th layer (mm)	Maximum strength (Pa)
0 mm	0mm	0mm	7.0×10^8	4 mm	0mm	0mm	7.0×10^8
0 mm	0mm	2mm	7.4×10^8	4 mm	0mm	2mm	7.2×10^8
0 mm	0mm	4mm	8.0×10^8	4 mm	0mm	4mm	7.8×10^8
0 mm	0mm	5mm	8.0×10^8	4 mm	0mm	5mm	7.8×10^8
0 mm	2mm	0mm	7.6×10^8	4 mm	2mm	0mm	7.0×10^8
0 mm	2mm	2mm	6.5×10^8	4 mm	2mm	2mm	7.5×10^8
0 mm	2mm	4mm	7.4×10^8	4 mm	2mm	4mm	7.4×10^8
0 mm	2mm	5mm	7.9×10^8	4 mm	2mm	5mm	7.9×10^8
0 mm	4mm	0mm	7.8×10^8	4 mm	4mm	0mm	7.5×10^8
0 mm	4mm	2mm	7.8×10^8	4 mm	4mm	2mm	7.8×10^8
0 mm	4mm	4mm	7.5×10^8	4 mm	4mm	4mm	7.2×10^8
0 mm	4mm	5mm	7.2×10^8	4 mm	4mm	5mm	7.0×10^8
0 mm	5mm	0mm	7.8×10^8	4 mm	5mm	0mm	7.5×10^8
0 mm	5mm	2mm	7.8×10^8	4 mm	5mm	2mm	7.8×10^8
0 mm	5mm	4mm	7.5×10^8	4 mm	5mm	4mm	7.3×10^8
0 mm	5mm	5mm	7.5×10^8	4 mm	5mm	5mm	7.3×10^8
2 mm	0mm	0mm	7.1×10^8	5 mm	0mm	0mm	7.2×10^8
2 mm	0mm	2mm	7.0×10^8	5 mm	0mm	2mm	7.9×10^8
2 mm	0mm	4mm	7.8×10^8	5 mm	0mm	4mm	8.1×10^8
2 mm	0mm	5mm	7.9×10^8	5 mm	0mm	5mm	8.4×10^8
2 mm	2mm	0mm	7.4×10^8	5 mm	2mm	0mm	7.5×10^8
2 mm	2mm	2mm	7.2×10^8	5 mm	2mm	2mm	7.6×10^8
2 mm	2mm	4mm	7.0×10^8	5 mm	2mm	4mm	7.0×10^8
2 mm	2mm	5mm	7.7×10^8	5 mm	2mm	5mm	7.8×10^8
2 mm	4mm	0mm	7.7×10^8	5 mm	4mm	0mm	8.0×10^8
2 mm	4mm	2mm	7.3×10^8	5 mm	4mm	2mm	7.8×10^8
2 mm	4mm	4mm	7.3×10^8	5 mm	4mm	4mm	7.6×10^8
2 mm	4mm	5mm	6.8×10^8	5 mm	4mm	5mm	7.4×10^8
2 mm	5mm	0mm	6.8×10^8	5 mm	5mm	0mm	7.5×10^8
2 mm	5mm	2mm	7.0×10^8	5 mm	5mm	2mm	7.6×10^8
2 mm	5mm	4mm	7.3×10^8	5 mm	5mm	4mm	7.4×10^8
2 mm	5mm	5mm	7.3×10^8	5 mm	5mm	5mm	7.9×10^8

5 SUMMARY

In this research, the influence of phase shift on woven laminates under uniaxial compression and biaxial compression is studied. The results show that the maximum strength of laminates under uniaxial compression and biaxial compression is significantly influenced by microstructure arrangement (phase shift) within the unit cell. The value of tangential stiffness for each laminates changes under uniaxial compression and biaxial compression as deformation increases.

Comparing the tangential stiffness among different laminates, one can conclude that tangential stiffness among different laminates changes under uniaxial compression. However, tangential stiffness among different laminates don't differ much under biaxial compression. By changing the phase shift among different layers of laminae, the maximum strength can be obtained. Using one homogenized modulus obtained from one layer of lamina cannot represent the responses of 64 laminates. How we come up with a representative cell including enough microstructure information such that it can represent the responses of these 64 laminates is the topic for future investigation.

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